

The Main Directions of Naming Model

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ABSTRACT: Each language has its own linguistic laws of name creation. Regardless of the field in which Naming technology works as a type of activity, its main goal in linguistics is to develop linguistic norms for the creation of a specific language-specific name. Every name, developed in accordance with linguistic norms, should help trade, production facilities, products to be competitive in the market, to develop, gain fame and spread widely. This article analyzes a number of requirements and criteria for name creation in linguistics, developed by Neimer-practitioners, and analyzes the models of name creation in the Uzbek language.

KEYWORDS: naming, name, naming technology, name creation, naming-modelirovanie.

INTRODUCTION

The history of naming began with the development of production and increased competition. It was necessary to distinguish the goods among the various goods. In the past, companies took the names of their founders, whose last name guarantees a certain quality of the product. "The naming base was built in the late 19th century, when the struggle for the consumer in America took on a larger scale. The name as a field of professional activity appeared in the early twentieth century.

Each language has its own linguistic laws of name creation. In particular, the names of production and trade facilities, products, their brand (brand), first of all, should be able to provide basic information about the object or product, as well as national-cultural views and perceptions of language owners. Through the name in the human mind is formed an image of the objects of production and trade, products, the most important aspects of their brand. The sum of such perceptions leads to the formation in the human mind of an image of a product, its brand, or an object of production. Of course, a particular product or object of production, such an image of brands is a semantic image enriched with national-cultural views, worldviews, perceptions, subjective attitudes.

While names reflect the perceptions of language owners about an object, their national-cultural views, the study of them in relation to the human factor that perceives it helps to identify specific national aspects of the naming mechanism in each language. The object of study of linguoculturology is the study of national and cultural aspects of a particular nation, which are reflected in the names of various production and trade objects, products, their trademarks (brands).

As a type of activity, Naming's technology, no matter what the field of collaboration, its main goal in linguistics is to develop linguistic norms for the creation of a specific language-specific name. Every name, developed in accordance with linguistic norms, should help trade, production facilities, products to be competitive in the market, to develop, gain fame and spread widely. In recent years, a number of requirements and criteria for the creation of a name by linguist-practitioners in linguistics have been developed. In particular, L.P. Kazanskaya pointed out the following criteria for name creation:

1. the word should sound melodic and beautiful, easy to read and pronounce;
2. should not form two different meaningful phonetic associations;
3. the word must have a clear and definite accent;
4. the chosen name should not lead to two different interpretations;
5. name must have clear semantics and be easy to remember;
6. Name should have only positive semantics. (1. 94)

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

According to the scientist, the list of these criteria should be expanded due to grammatical, verbal and methodological criteria. He expands the criteria for creating a name based on the study of ergonomics created in Tolyatti in the last 5 years with the following linguistic requirements:

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- 1) Phonologically: the title should be easily pronounced in one or more languages;
- 2) The graphic representation of the name allows the sound image to be uniformly expressed using alphabetical symbols and provides stability in the visual perception of the name, which is especially important for the international level of the name;
- 3) It is divided into more interesting conclusions through the lexical analysis of its. On demand, the Names need to strengthen their marketing goals. The ambiguity of a word in relation to its figurative meanings should not undermine the idea conveyed by its basic meaning: the noun should provide a connection with the nominative and reflect a sufficiently po-hyperonymic relationship;
- 4) Grammatically, in the formation of names, of course, definite names predominate: Like “Ribbon”, “Pyramid”, “Behemoth”, “Orange”, “Watermelon”. “Triumph” and “Prestige” are common and rarely used;
- 5) shows the predominance of neutral lexical units in the stylistic analysis of name, in some cases there is a sub-style lexicon of store names, such as “Khalyava”, but the upper stylistic names are not observed...;
- 6) The obsolete lexicon has its substitute units and is expressed almost in Cyrillic;
- 7) The main aspect of the stylistic aspect of Name's activity can be considered: the name should correspond to the style of the firm;
- 8) In the associative aspect, noun-derived masonry associations play an important role, it is preferable that semantic associations with two different meanings be avoided;
- 9) There are mistakes in Name's work in terms of compliance with the norms of literary language: “Rybachek”, “Rusich” stores ... (2. 95-97)

V. Yu. Kojanova notes that the following rules should be followed when creating a brand name:

1. The brand name should be easy to pronounce.
2. The brand name should be phonetically literate in order to be remembered as easily as possible.
3. It is necessary to create a brand name by studying different languages so that it does not form random associations in other languages.
4. The brand name should be perceived positively in a subjective sense. (3.13)

“There are not only linguistic, but also psychological, national and cultural criteria for creating a name in a language. The name should be linguistically perfect, but should not have a negative impact on the human psyche, should be in line with the national and cultural views of the speakers, the national moral standards [4. 5].

It is especially important to follow the lexical norms of the language when creating a name.

Uzbek names created over the past years for production, trade, enterprises, firms and products in our country are lexically diverse. When we look at the lexical structure of the names used in practice, we see that in the creation of the name, along with Uzbek words, a mixture of foreign words was used. In the Uzbek name creation system, along with its own layer units, there are many cases of using self-leveling units. Such names can be divided into the following types according to their components:

1. Names formed with their own language units (or units that have become their own language units): “RAYKHON”, “YALPIZ” (names of public catering establishments), “KOKCHA KOSHONASI”, “MUMTOZ” (names of restaurants, weddings).
2. Names formed with other language units: “DABANA”, “PROTEIN”, “TEXNO-SOFT”, “EXCELLENT EAST”, “GRAND-DUET”, “AVA REK” (names of limited liability companies); “RUXSALIS”, “DAYEL WORLD” (private enterprises).
3. Names formed with their own and other language units: “KAFOLAT PRINT COMPANY”, “NOZ-SHEDEV”, “KAMTAR-NEO”, “SAIDKOMOL KONSALT”, “MUNAVVAR MARKET”, “AMIRSAID-LYUKS” (names of limited liability companies). It is no secret that in addition to their own language units, there are cases of forming names with other language units. Such names are created in English, Russian or with the participation of these language units and are widely used in business.

The use of anthroponyms, in particular, is widespread in the practice of name creation.

The practice of using anthroponyms in name creation has existed since time immemorial. In the past, there have been many cases in which anonymous names have been used to form names with anthroponyms. It is known that naming a particular object after a celebrity has a specific purpose. Such names serve the purpose of further glorifying, honoring and remembering the names of those who were honored for their great services to the country. For example, “ZANGI OTA”, “MANNON UYGUR” neighborhood citizens' meeting, “OYBEK” metro station, “MIRZO ULUGBEK” metro station, etc.

In recent years, as anthroponyms, the names of production, trade object, the owner of the firm or his parents, grandparents, children are often taken. For example, we see that the following names of consumer services in Shayhantahur district of Tashkent are based on human names: “ZULKHUMOR” Women's Salon, “OMINA-OQILA” Limited Liability Company.

Sometimes in the structure of the name, along with the name of the person, the use of words denoting his personal qualities is also observed. For example, the name of the limited liability company “MIRZAAHMAD OTA”, the lexeme of the father used in the

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names of the private enterprise “OQILKHON OTA” provide information about the social role of the person in society. Such names can give an idea of the founder, owner of an enterprise, firm, society, etc., its social role, occupation, gender, but, unfortunately, do not give any information about a particular object, firm, enterprise or manufactured product.

The interest in creating a name with anthroponyms is growing, especially after independence. In creating these types of names, it is clear that factors such as purpose, necessity, which are primarily related to the personality of the language owner, were taken into account. However, the principles of word-formation specific to a particular language should not be overlooked when creating a new name.

Names formed with anthroponyms seem to take into account the following communicative goals of language owners:

- 1) refer to the owner of the production, trade object, enterprise, firm (or his relatives): Private firm “AKMAL ABZALOV”, private enterprises “JORA OTA OG'LI ISMOIL”, “NOSIRKHOJA”;
- 2) to indicate the type of production, trade object, enterprise, firm owner and the activity carried out by him: Limited Liability Companies “YASMINA-TUR”, “KABIL-KANDOLAT”, “MAXLIYO-SHIFO”; private companies like “JO'RA-IMORAT” and “BEHRUZ-STOM”;
- 3) reference to the profession of the owner of the production, trade object, enterprise, firm: “EGAMBERDI OSHPAZ” Limited Liability Company; Private enterprise “DOKTOR OKTAM”;
- 4) production, trade object, enterprise, company owner's social role, position, gender: “MAXAMAT-OTA”, “SHAYKH-ALINUR”, “KHADICHA HOJI ONA SERVICE” private enterprises; Private companies “R.YUNUS-OTA”, “LATIFBEKHOJI”; Limited Liability Company “MUMIN-OQ SOQOL”; Private company “NODIROVA”;
- 5) refer to the owner of the production, trade object, enterprise, firm (or his relatives) and express a subjective attitude: Private enterprise “BARNO-OY”, “ZIYODA BEGIM”, “IQBOLBEGIM” Limited Liability Company. Apparently, names created with anthroponyms directly reflect personality traits.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of names used in the practice of name creation shows that the norms of the Uzbek language are not always followed in the creation of names. There are also cases when non-compliance with the established norms of language in the creation of names has led to the failure and ineffectiveness of names. In particular, in the names created in recent years, along with the names of people, there is a parallel use of units related to the activities of enterprises, firms, trade facilities. For example, the use of Uzbek names in the names of private enterprises “AZAMJON OTA BIZNES”, “MARHAMAT ONA SERVIS”, as well as assimilations reflecting the activities of enterprises and firms, not only violates the methodological norms of our language, but also makes the name a laughing stock.

Thus, the correct and purposeful use of the possibilities of language in the creation of a new name serves to ensure the success of the name.

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